

A modified spray reagent for the identification of amino acids on thin layer chromatography plates

S. Laskar^{*}, A. Sinhababu and K. M. Hazra

Natural Products Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, India
E-mail : burchdsa@cal.vsnl.net.in

Manuscript received 3 March 2000, accepted 26 August 2000

A modified ninhydrin spray reagent, 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid-ninhydrin is capable of developing various distinguishable colours with many of the amino acids on thin layer plates. The detection limits for amino acids with this spray reagent range from 0.1 to 1.0 μg and 0.01 to 0.8 μg under two conditions.

Identification of amino acids has immense importance because they are the backbone of proteins and also exist in free state in natural products. Though several specific and non-specific reagents^{1,2} have been proposed by different workers for the detection of amino acids on thin layer chromatograms, still ninhydrin is popular for its remarkable high sensitivity², yet there is a difficulty in identifying amino acids due to the formation of identical colour (purple/blue) with all amino acids except proline and hydroxyproline. Thus, a modification of ninhydrin colour reaction is somewhat essential to solve this problem. This communication reveals a modification of ninhydrin spray with 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid as auxiliary spray reagent.

Results and Discussion

It is observed from Table 1 that ninhydrin gives various colours with amino acids in presence of auxiliary reagent (3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid) before and after final heating. The detection limits in most cases lie between 0.01 to 1 μg which is merely comparable to ninhydrin alone (Table 1). In most cases the detection limits are either equal or a little higher than those obtained after final heating. Such colour formation with high sensitivities of this modified spray reagent makes it somewhat more useful than ninhydrin spray in the detection of amino acids on TLC plates.

The mechanism leading to the colour development is uncertain. One possibility is the formation of a secondary amide by the reaction between 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid with amino acids and the product thus obtained forms colouring complexes with ninhydrin, colours of which are variable depending on the nature of the amino acids.

Table 1. Colour formations of amino acids with ninhydrin in the presence of 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid on TLC plates

Amino acid	Colour observed in cold condition [*]	Detection limit μg	Colour observed after heating	Detection limit μg
Glycine	Brownish red	1.0	Lilac	0.5
Alanine	Lilac	1.0	Reddish violet	0.7
Valine	Reddish pink	1.0	Pinkish violet	0.3
Leucine	Pale rose	0.1	Pinkish violet	0.06
Isoleucine	Light violet	0.4	Pale rose	0.4
Serine	Pale lilac	1.0	Bluish violet	0.01
Threonine	Dirty pink	6.0	Dirty pink	1.0
Aspartic acid	Light violet	2.0	Lilac	0.4
Asparagine	Reddish pink	1.0	Pinkish violet	0.1
Glutamic acid	Pink	1.0	Reddish pink	0.01
Glutamine	Pinkish violet	0.1	Reddish violet	0.02
Lysine	Pale lilac	0.1	Wild lilac	0.05
Histidine	Reddish violet	1.0	Reddish violet	0.8
Arginine	Brownish pink	0.1	Brownish pink	0.02
Phenylalanine	Mist grey	0.1	Pinkish grey	0.06
Tyrosine	Pinkish white	0.1	Greenish white	0.1
Tryptophan	Pale lilac	1.0	Pale lilac	0.2
Cysteine	Apple white	1.0	Reddish violet	0.04
Cystine	Rose white	1.0	Pale lilac	0.4
Methionine	Light violet	1.0	Greyish pink	0.7
Proline	Yellow	1.0	Brownish yellow	0.04
Hydroxyproline	Pale lilac	1.0	Grey	0.04

^{*} Colour observed after 20 min of spraying ninhydrin reagent

Experimental

Thin layer chromatographic plates (20 × 20 cm, thickness 0.1 mm) were prepared with silica gel G (Merck) by using Unoplan coating apparatus (Shandon).

Standard solutions (1 mg ml⁻¹) of amino acids (Sigma) were prepared in a 0.01 mol dm⁻³ phosphate buffer (pH 8.0). The spray reagents used were 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (Spectrochem) and ninhydrin (Sigma).

Procedure :

Sample solutions were applied onto thin layer chromatoplates by means of calibrated micropipette (25 µl). After developing in *n*-propanol and water mixture (70 + 30, v/v)², the plates were dried and sprayed with a 0.01% solution of 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid in ethanol. The plates were then dried in air and heated to 110° for 10 min and then sprayed with a 0.25% solution of ninhydrin in acetone. The plates were again air-dried and colours noted. Colours were further observed after heating the plates at 110° for 10 min. Colours and detection limits for the amino acids investigated were observed before second heating (20

min after spraying the latter reagent) and after second heating.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. E. Chargaff, C. Levine and C. Green, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1948, **175**, 67; G. Toennies and J. J. Kolb, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 823; G. Curzon and J. Giltrow, *Nature (London)*, 1953, **172**, 356; R. Con-sden, A. H. Gordon and A. J. P. Martin, *Biochem. J.*, 1946, **40**, 580; S. R. Dickmann and A. L. Crockett, 1956, **220**, 957; H. R. Mahler and E. H. Cordes, "Basic Biological Chemistry", Harper & Row, New York, 1968; G. Pataki, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1964, **16**, 541; T. Wolski, W. Golkiewicz and A. Rompala, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 1980, **25**, 583; W. Distler, *Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1981, **309**, 127; K. Lorentz and B. Flatter, *Anal. Biochem.*, 1970, **38**, 557; G. Devaux and P. Mesnard, *Bull. Soc. Pharm. Bordeaux*, 1971, **110**, 145; S. Laskar and B. Basak, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1988, **436**, 341; *J. Planar Chromatogr.*, 1990, **3**, 275, 535; B. Basak and S. Laskar, *Talanta*, 1990, **37**, 1105; B. Basak, U. K. Bhattacharya and S. Laskar, *Amino Acids*, 1993, **4**, 193; A. Sinhababu, B. Basak and S. Laskar, *Anal. Proc.*, 1994, **31**, 65.
2. E. Stahl, "Thin Layer Chromatography : A Laboratory Handbook", Springer, New York, 1969.